

Factors affecting with Implementation of Good Quality Service at Tiom Hospital Public Sub Province Lanny Jaya

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ABSTRACT

Background: Hospital represents one of the health service institutions which are vital to be mounted by society. Officer which look out on direct with moment society give service represent especial source in executing prima service, for that officer require to get special attention. The mentioned because of most cause of satisfaction customer/client in health service from officer behavior in giving excellent service, but the excellent service in Tiom Hospital uncommitted better. Research of subjective to know factor - factor related to uncommitting of excellent service in Tiom Hospital Sub Province Lanny Jaya.

Method Research: Analytic by using cross sectional study of conducted in October 2017 with amount of sample counted 48 people. Data approach used questionnaire and analyzed by chi square.

Result of research: The factors related to the excellent service at Tiom Hospital, Lanny Jaya Regency are reciprocal salaries (p-value = 0.006; RP = 2.402; CI95% = 1.201 - 4.804), variety of expertise (p-value = 0.000; RP = 19.286; CI95% = 2,851 - 130,455), assignment attributes (p-value = 0.007; RP = 3.095; CI95% = 1.122 - 8.535), autonomy (p-value = 0.036; RP = 2.011; CI95% = 1.017 - 3.976), feedback (p-value = 0.002; RP = 2.538; CI95% = 1.339 - 4.813), organizational commitment (p-value = 0,000; RP = 2.747; CI95% = 1.645 - 4.488) and leadership of the Head of the Room (p-value = 0.013; RP = 2,143; CI95% = (1,136-441). Factors related to gender (p-value = 1,000; RP = 0.947; CI95% = 0.564 - 1.591), education (p-value = 0.488; RP = 1.267; CI95% = (0.771 - 2.081), working period (p-value = 0.283; RP = 1.510; CI95% = (0.785 - 2.903), task

significance (p-value = 0.226; RP = 1.500; CI95% = 0.844 - 2.666) and co-workers (p-value = 0.170; RP = 1.523; CI95% = (0.901 - 2.574).

Key Words: Excellent Quality Service, Employee, Tiom Hospital

INTRODUCTION

The Hospital is a vital health care institution at the community level. In the current era of globalization, people have a high awareness of their rights to get public services, hospitals as one of the public service organizations must provide fast, quality and professional services. The hospital must be patient oriented (Customer Oriented) which can be realized by providing excellent service.

Employees who are dealing directly with the community while providing services are the main source in carrying out excellent service. Good employee performance can have a positive impact on the entire service process that has contributed to excellent service. Lanny Jaya Regional General Hospital is one of the hospitals in Lanny Jaya Regency which is trying to provide excellent service to the community in its working area in accordance with the Decree of the Minister of Administrative Reform No. 63 / KEP / M.PAN / 7/2003 concerning General Guidelines for the Implementation of Public Services. It is also stated in the Vision of Tiom District Hospital, Lanny Jaya Regency, which states that it always

provides excellent service to realize an independent society for healthy living.

In general, the quality of service at Tiom District Hospital Lanny Jaya District is not optimal and there is patient dissatisfaction with the element of prime assessment especially in the field of nursing. The results of the interview in the Nursing Service Section in August 2017 were in accordance with the responses and complaints submitted in the suggestion box in the Tiom Regional General Hospital, Lanny Jaya Regency, namely the complaints of the general public regarding the services provided, especially in the services at Tiom District Hospital Lanny Jaya District, as said- words that are less pleasant and services that are less satisfactory, so that the community or patients as recipients of services are not in line with their expectations. From the results of interviews of 10 patients or the community are still not satisfied with the services provided to the community / patients tend to be less and not qualified, especially in the attitude of employees who are less friendly, impolite and unfriendly and less attention to complaints perceived by the community or patient.

This is the cause of customer dissatisfaction with the health services of the officers' behavior in providing services, so that in this excellent service that refers to several points, namely the ability (ability), attitude (attitude), appearance (Appearance), attention (attention), action (action) and accountability is the topic of researchers in excellent service. This is based on the service provided at Tiom District Hospital, Lanny Jaya Regency, which has not yet been assessed by the management of Tiom Hospital and other researchers, so that the findings of the above problems make researchers interested in studying this topic in more depth in a scientific study to be able to see excellent service quality.

Based on this problem, the researcher is interested in conducting research on factors related to excellent service at Tiom Regional General Hospital,

Lanny Jaya District as government-owned health services, so that the factors that become obstacles can be overcome and the factors that support employees in providing services can be paid more attention. The purpose of this study was to determine the factors related to the excellent service at Tiom Regional General Hospital, Lanny Jaya District

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Analytical using a cross sectional study approach conducted in October 2017 with a total sample of 33 people. Data were obtained using questionnaires and analyzed using chi square.

RESULTS

Independent and Dependent Variables

Bivariate Analysis

Influence of Age with excellent service

Table1. Relationship of Age with excellent service at RSUD Tiom, Lanny Jaya District, 2017

No	Age	Excellent service				Number	
		Low		High		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	< 30 year	22	75,9	7	24,1	29	100
2	> 30 year	6	31,6	13	68,4	19	100
Total		28	58,3	20	41,7	48	100
<i>p-value = 0,006; RP = 2,402; CI95%= (1,201 – 4,804)</i>							

Table 1, shows that from 29 employees with age <30 years as many as 22 people (75.9%) have low service and high excellent service as many as 7 people (24.1%). Whereas from 19 employees with age > 30 years as many as 6 people (58.3%) had a low level of excellent service and high excellent service as many as 13 people (68.4%). Chi square test results obtained p-value = 0.006 <0.05. This means that there is an age relationship with excellent service at the Tiom Regional General Hospital, Lanny Jaya District. The ratio test results obtained Rp = 2.402; CI95% = (1,201 - 4,804) interpreted that employees who are <30 years old tend to have excellent service performance that is less than 2,402 times higher than employees who have the same age above 30 years.

Gender Relationship with excellent service

Table2. Gender Relationship with excellent service at Tiom District Hospital Lanny Jaya Regency in 2017

No	Sex	Excellent service				Number	
		Low		High		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	Male	9	56,3	7	43,8	16	100
2	Female	19	59,4	13	40,6	32	100
Total		28	58,3	20	41,7	48	100
<i>p-value = 1,000; RP = 0,947; CI95%=(0,564 – 1,591)</i>							

Table 2 shows that of the 16 employees with male gender as many as 9 people (56.3%) had low service and high excellent service as many as 7 people (43.8%). While from 32 employees with female gender as many as 19 people (59.4%) had low service and high excellent service as many as 13 people (40.6%). Chi square test results obtained $p\text{-value} = 1,000 > 0.05$. This means that there is no meaningful relationship between the sexes and the excellent service at Tiom District Hospital Lanny Jaya Regency.

Educational Relations with excellent service

Table3. Relationship of Education with excellent service at Tiom District Hospital Lanny Jaya District in 2017

No	Education	Excellent service				Number	
		Low		High		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	Low	7	70	3	30	10	100
2	High	21	55,3	17	44,7	38	100
Total		28	58,3	20	41,7	48	100
<i>p-value = 0,488; RP = 1,267; CI95%=(0,771 – 2,081)</i>							

Table 3, shows that out of 10 low-educated employees, 7 people (70%) have low service and high excellent service as many as 3 people (30%). While from 38 employees with higher education as many as 21 people (55.3%) had a low level of excellent service and high excellent service as many as 17 people (44.7%). The chi square test results obtained $p\text{-value} = 0.488 > 0.05$. This means that there is no meaningful relationship between education and excellent service at RSUD Tiom, Lanny Jaya District.

Relationship with the best service

Table4. Relationship with the service period excellent service at Tiom Hospital Lanny Jaya District in 2017

No	Working period	Excellent service				Number	
		Low		High		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	New	22	64,7	12	35,3	34	100
2	Long	6	42,9	8	57,1	14	100
Total		28	58,3	20	41,7	48	100
<i>p-value = 0,283; RP = 1,510; CI95%=(0,785 – 2,903)</i>							

Table 4 shows that of the 34 new working people as many as 22 people (64.7%) have low service and high excellent service as many as 12 people (35.3%). Whereas from 14 employees with long service life as many as 6 people (42.9%) had low service and high excellent service as many as 8 people (57.1%). Chi square test results obtained $p\text{-value} = 0.283 > 0.05$. This means that there is no meaningful relationship between the period of service and excellent service at RSUD Tiom, Lanny Jaya Regency.

Variety of expertise with excellent service

Table5. Relationship Variety of expertise with excellent service at RSUD Tiom Lanny Jaya Regency in 2017

No	Level expertise	Excellent service				Number	
		Low		High		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	Low	27	96,4	1	3,6	28	100
2	High	1	5	19	95	20	100
Total		28	58,3	20	41,7	48	100
<i>p-value = 0,000; RP = 19,286; CI95%=(2,851 – 130,455)</i>							

Table 5, shows that from 28 employees with a low level of expertise as many as 27 people (96.4%) had a low level of excellent service and high excellent service as much as 1 person (3.6%). While from 20 employees with a high level of expertise as many as 1 person (5%) had a low level of excellent service and high excellent service as many as 19 people (95%). Chi square test results obtained $p\text{-value} = 0,000 < 0,05$. This means that there is a variety of expertise with excellent service at Tiom District Hospital Lanny Jaya District. Ratio test results obtained $R_p = 19,286$; $CI95\% = (2,851 - 130,455)$ interpreted that employees who have a low level of expertise tend to have excellent service performance that is less than 14.167

times higher than employees who have a high level of expertise.

Task Identity Relationship with excellent service

Table 6. Task Identity Relationship with excellent service at Tiom Regional Hospital Lanny Jaya District in 2017

No	Task identity	Excellent service				Number	
		Low		High			
		n	%	n	%		%
1	Low	25	71,4	10	28,6	35	100
2	High	3	23,1	10	76,9	13	100
Total		28	58,3	20	41,7	48	100

p-value = 0,007; RP = 3,095; CI95% = (1,122 – 8,535)

Table 6 shows that of 35 employees with low task identities as many as 25 people (71.4%) had low service and high excellent service as many as 10 people (28.6%). Whereas from 13 employees with high duty identities as many as 3 people (23.1%) had low service and high excellent service as many as 10 people (76.9%). Chi square test results obtained $p\text{-value} = 0.007 < 0.05$. This means that there is a task identity relationship with excellent service at Tiom District Hospital Lanny Jaya District. Ratio test results obtained $Rp = 3.095$; $CI95\% = (1,122 - 8,535)$ interpreted that low task identities have a low service performance of 3,095 times higher than those with a high task identity.

Relationship between Duty Significance and excellent service

Table7. Relationship between the Significance of Tasks and excellent service at Tiom Regional General Hospital, Lanny Jaya Regency, 2017

No	Task Significance	Excellent service				Number	
		Low		High			
		n	%	n	%		%
1	Low	20	66,7	10	33,3	30	100
2	High	8	44,4	10	55,6	18	100
Total		28	58,3	20	41,7	48	100

p-value = 0,226; RP = 1,500; CI95% = (0,844 – 2,666)

Table 7, shows that of 30 employees with low task significance as many as 20 people (66.7%) had low service and high excellent service as many as 10 people (33.3%). Whereas from 18 employees with high task significance as many as 8 people (44.4%) had low excellent service and high excellent service as many as 10 people

(55.6%). Chi square test results obtained $p\text{-value} = 0.226 > 0.05$. This means that there is no relationship between the significance of the task and the excellent service at the Tiom Regional General Hospital, Lanny Jaya Regency. The results of the ratio test were $Rp = 1,500$; $CI95\% = (0.844 - 2.666)$ with a lower value of less than 1, so it is not meaningful.

Autonomous Relations with excellent service

Table 8. Autonomous Relations with excellent service at Tiom Hospital Lanny Jaya District in 2017

No	Otonomi	Pelayanan Prima				Jumlah	
		Rendah		Tinggi			
		n	%	n	%		%
1	Rendah	22	71	9	29	31	100
2	Tinggi	6	35,3	11	64,7	17	100
Total		28	58,3	20	41,7	48	100

p-value = 0,036; RP = 2,011; CI95% = (1,017 – 3,976)

Table 8, shows that of 31 employees with low autonomy, 22 people (71%) had low service and high excellent services were 9 people (29%). Whereas from 17 employees with high autonomy as many as 6 people (35.3%) had a low level of excellent service and high excellent service as many as 11 people (64.7%). Chi square test results obtained $p\text{-value} = 0.036 < 0.05$. This means that there is an autonomous relationship with excellent service at Tiom Regional General Hospital, Lanny Jaya Regency. The ratio test results obtained $Rp = 2.011$; $CI95\% = (1,017 - 3,976)$ interpreted that employees who have low autonomy tend to have excellent service performance which is less 2,011 times higher than employees who have autonomy

Feedback relationship with excellent service

Table9. Relationship Feedback with excellent service at RSUD Tiom Lanny Jaya Regency in 2017

No	Feedback	Excellent service				Number	
		Low		High			
		n	%	n	%		%
1	Low	21	80,8	5	19,2	26	100
2	High	7	31,8	15	68,2	22	100
Total		28	58,3	20	41,7	48	100

p-value = 0,002; RP = 2,538; CI95% = (1,339 – 4,813)

Table 9, shows that from 267 employees with low feedback as many as 21 people (80.8%) had a low level of excellent service and high excellent service as many as 5 people (19.2%). Whereas from 22 employees with high feedback as many as 7 people (31.8%) had a low level of excellent service and high excellent service as many as 15 people (68.2%). Chi square test results obtained p -value = 0.002 < 0.05. This means that there is a feedback relationship with excellent service at Tiom District Hospital Lanny Jaya Regency. The results of the ratio test were Rp. 2.538; CI95% = (1,339 - 4,813) interpreted that employees who have low feedback tend to have low service performance that is 2,538 times higher than employees who have high feedback.

Organizational Commitment Relationship with excellent service

Table10. Relationship between organizational commitment and excellent service at Tiom Hospital Lanny Jaya District in 2017

No	organizational commitment	Excellent service				Number	
		Low		High		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	Low	18	94,7	1	5,3	19	100
2	High	10	34,5	19	65,5	29	100
Total		28	58,3	20	41,7	48	100
<i>p</i> -value = 0,000; RP = 2,747; CI95%= (1,645 - 4,588)							

Table 10, shows that from 19 employees with low organizational commitment as many as 18 people (94.7%) had low service and high excellent service as much as 1 person (8.3%). Whereas from 29 employees with high organizational commitment as many as 10 people (34.5%) had low service and high excellent service as many as 19 people (65.5%). Chi square test results obtained p -value = 0,000 < 0,05. This means that there is a relationship between organizational commitment and excellent service at Tiom District Hospital Lanny Jaya District. The results of the ratio test were Rp. 2.747; CI95% = (1,645 - 4,588) interpreted that employees who have low organizational commitment tend to have excellent service performance that is less 2,747 times higher than employees who have high organizational commitment.

Co-worker relations with excellent service

Table11. Relationship between colleagues and excellent service at Tiom Hospital Lanny Jaya District in 2017

No	Co-worker relationships	Excellent service				Number	
		Low		High		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	Low	18	69,2	8	30,8	26	100
2	High	10	45,5	12	54,5	22	100
Total		28	58,3	20	41,7	48	100
<i>p</i> -value = 0,170; RP = 1,523; CI95%= (0,901 - 2,574)							

Table 11 shows that of 26 employees with low co-worker relationships as many as 18 people (69.2%) had low service and high excellent service as many as 8 people (30.8%). Whereas from 22 employees with high co-worker relationships as many as 10 people (45.5%) had low service and high excellent service as many as 12 people (54.5%). Chi square test results obtained p -value = 0.170 > 0.05. This means that there is no relationship between colleagues and excellent service at Tiom District Hospital, Lanny Jaya Regency. The result of the ratio test is Rp = 1,523; CI95% = (0.901 - 2.574) which is meaningless.

Head Leadership Relationships with excellent service

Table12. Leadership Relationship Head of Room with excellent service at Tiom Regional General Hospital, Lanny Jaya District, 2017

No	Leaderships	Excellent service				Number	
		Low		High		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	Low	21	75	7	25	28	100
2	High	7	35	13	65	20	100
Total		28	58,3	20	41,7	48	100
<i>p</i> -value = 0,013; RP = 2,143; CI95%= (1,136 - 4,041)							

Table 12, shows that from 28 employees with low leadership as many as 21 people (75%) have low service and high excellent service as many as 7 people (25%). Whereas from 20 employees with high leadership as many as 7 people (35%) have low service and high excellent service as many as 13 people (65%). Chi square test results obtained p -value = 0.013 < 0.05. This means that there is a leadership relationship with excellent service at RSUD Tiom, Lanny Jaya District. The results of the ratio test obtained Rp = 2.143; CI95% = (1,136 -

4,041) interpreted that employees who have low leadership tend to have excellent service performance that is 2,447 times higher than employees who have high leadership.

DISCUSSION

Overview of Excellent Services Employees at Tiom Hospital Lanny Jaya District

The results of the research conducted at Tiom Hospital towards 48 employees who provide services directly to patients or visitors of Tiom Hospital, showed as many as 28 employees (58.3%) were low in providing excellent service to patients or visitors. In this study, excellent service was assessed by researchers through direct observation when employees were providing services to Puskesmas patients. Overall, Tiom Hospital employees have provided good service, but in part the service staff provided cannot be said to be excellent.

Analysis of Factors that have not been carried out by the Excellent Service Employees at Tiom Regional General Hospital

Influence of Age with excellent service

Excellent service which is a strategic issue in the world of services, attracts every organization that sells services / services to be able to provide services that exceed community expectations. The application of excellent service aims to improve the quality of service which also impacts the satisfaction of the community as service users. Tiom Hospital is one of the hospitals in Lanny Jaya District which has begun to try to apply a culture of excellent service to employees. But not all employees can carry out excellent service in accordance with the components of excellent service, one of the factors that is suspected to affect employees in providing excellent service is the age of employees.

Older employees are less likely to leave or quit their jobs and low levels of absenteeism. But of all the advantages

possessed by older employees, there are some disadvantages such as lack of flexibility and rejecting new technology. The results of the study show the same thing that not excellent service is mostly done by employees over 30 years of age. According to Padmowihardjo (2012) someone who has the age of <30 years will be able to learn faster and can maintain learning achievement if given a good tutoring.

Padmowihardjo (2012) added that although employees over 30 years of age can still develop their learning abilities, the results achieved will not be better than employees under 30 years of age and under. This is influenced by factors that have a relationship between age and one's ability to learn, namely the mechanism of learning that is influenced by the maturity of the brain, sensual organs and muscles of certain organs. In addition, the relationship between age and one's ability is also influenced by the accumulation of experience and other learning processes. For younger employees, their learning abilities are also supported by great enthusiasm at work. Young employees who have just graduated will be more enthusiastic at work, because they only experience the experience of making their own money without having to ask parents. The results of this study prove the hypothesis of Robbins (2006) theory which states that there is a relationship between age and excellent service of employees. Chi square analysis showed that there was a significant relationship between age and excellent service of Tiom Hospital employees in 2017 with p at 0.006.

A positive relationship indicates that service is not prime tends to be given by employees who are <30 years old. The existence of a meaningful relationship between age and excellent service employees shows that abilities and experiences that have less impact on employee motivation to be able to improve their performance by providing excellent service.

Relationship between Gender and Excellent Service Employees

According to Gibson (2006) the obedience and compliance of women in work will affect their performance personally. The results of this study did not show the same thing that is not excellent service is mostly done by female employees 19 employees (59.4%) compared to male employees by 9 employees (56.3%). Poor service conducted by female employees is thought to be caused by low expectations to be able to achieve success for some women who have married and become secondary income earners (Robbins and Timothy, 2009). Opinions that are widely developed in the community are also thought to have been inherent among women, namely that no matter how high the level of education and occupation of women, the main task of women is as a housewife. If it is based on such thoughts, female employees are less motivated to provide excellent service to patients. Female employees who are married are also required to be able to serve and take care of their families, so that their concentration in work can be divided between office tasks and their duties as housewives. A greater burden is also felt by women who already have children, they are required to be able to work while controlling and / or taking care of their children whenever and wherever.

The results of this study do not support the hypothesis of Robbins (2006) theory which states that there is a relationship between sexes and employee service. Chi square analysis showed that there was no significant relationship between sexes with the excellent service of Tiom Hospital employees in 2017 with p of 1,000. There was no meaningful relationship between the sexes and excellent service, because the duties and responsibilities of female employees were more than male employees. Most female employees are often included / given responsibility in the activities of the Tiom General Hospital outside the main duties of service. The difference in workload directly

or indirectly affects employees in providing excellent service.

Efforts that can be made to improve the excellent service of employees based on gender are by placing employees in accordance with the workplace or providing appropriate tasks. The placement of work units or the provision of basic tasks / additional tasks can be done through consideration of the ability and attitudes of employees in providing services to patients. In addition, there needs to be a fairer division of tasks outside the main task by involving male employees to take part or role. So that no employee gets a workload greater or far greater than other employees.

Relationship between Education and Excellent Service Employees

Service is not prime done by employees who have a higher level of education compared to employees who have a low education level of 7 employees (70%). Tiom Hospital staff consists of various levels of education, ranging from low education to higher education. The situation in the field shows that the majority of Tiom Hospital employees with higher education level are given more responsibility, that is given other tasks besides their main duties. The many tasks and responsibilities that they bear, can affect the employee in providing excellent service. Employees with more duties and responsibilities are expected to be unable to fully maximize their duties. When an employee performs one of his duties, the employee cannot concentrate fully, because he thinks of other tasks that have not been completed. As with other employees who have low education, they are rarely given additional tasks outside of their main duties. Therefore, in providing services, employees with education level are more focused on doing their tasks.

Relationship between Working Period and Excellent Service of Employees

The results of this study were obtained by excellent service by employees with a long service period compared to 22

employees with a new working period (64.7%). This is allegedly due to the long working culture that has been attached to employees who have worked for more than 3 years at Tiom Hospital. While employees with a service period of less than 3 years or not even reached 1 year, a culture of excellent service is easier to learn and apply when providing services to patients. The old work culture that developed in Tiom Regional Hospital was in the form of a serving culture that did not prioritize customer needs, was indifferent and did not serve with the heart. This culture is clearly in conflict with the culture of excellent service that prioritizes service from the heart. Therefore changing and instilling a culture of excellent service is not an easy thing, there needs to be a shared commitment and a strong desire to jointly provide excellent service to the community.

The experience of employees in dealing with patients is thought to also influence employees in providing excellent service. Field conditions indicate that employees with long working periods are considered to be very familiar with the various characters of patients who seek treatment at Tiom Hospital, so that employees with long working periods can handle patient problems / complaints based on their experience while working at Tiom Hospital. It is different with employees who have a service period of less than 1 year, because they do not know the various characteristics of patients who come / seek treatment at the health center, employees with new working periods will be more careful in providing services to avoid patient complaints. In addition, employees with new working periods (<1 year) are more enthusiastic or motivated to be able to show good performance to colleagues and leaders, so that they are more striving earnestly in providing excellent service.

The absence of a relationship between years of service and excellent service employees allegedly influenced by other factors such as, the period of service of the Civil Servants (PNS) which is a

policy of the Lanny Jaya District Health Office and not a right of the hospital management or the employee itself related to work placement. Efforts that can be made to be able to increase employee productivity in providing excellent service is by changing the organizational culture. The organizational culture that originally did not require employees to provide excellent service became an organizational culture that prioritized patient satisfaction by always striving to provide added value (excellent service) to patients / visitors of Tiom Hospital. The organizational culture must continue to be invested in employees through various opportunities such as briefing or employee meetings. Besides that, instilling a culture of serving with conscience can be done through trainings related to the culture of serving. After involving employees in the training, the next step that must be done by the management is to evaluate the results of the training regularly. It is intended that what has been delivered in the training can be practiced in daily activities, so that employees can provide excellent service to patients.

Relationship between Variety of Expertise and Excellent Service of Employees

The results of the study that the service is not prime is mostly done by employees with a low level of expertise compared to employees with a high level of expertise as many as 27 employees (96.4%). This is because with the least expertise needed in the work, employees will feel that their work is monotonous (no challenges). For Tiom Hospital employees, the majority of employees have a long working period, providing services that every day employees do to patients is not difficult. Employees feel they already know more and are more experienced in serving patients with various characteristics, so they will judge that the service they have done so far is good enough. Good enough here is not necessarily an excellent service (very good

service) that the community hopes they can feel at the health service of the Tiom District Hospital in the neighbourhood.

There is a relationship between the variety of skills and excellent service of employees, namely the different levels of expertise in each service unit and employee work based on the profession. For employees who have high intensity to deal directly with patients, the skills they need will be more diverse. This study also shows that there is a small difference in proportion between employees who have a low level of expertise and do not provide excellent service with employees who have a high level of expertise and do not provide excellent service.

Relationship between Task Identity and Staff Excellent Service

The results of this study indicate that low service excellence is mostly done by employees with low task identities compared to 25 employees with high duty identities (71.4%). For Tiom Hospital staff consisting of various levels of education and different job specifications, each employee should clearly know what to do at the same time be their responsibility. Employees who only know who must do their duty without assuming it is not responsible will reduce the level of task identity itself and will also have an impact on the excellent service it provides. If the employee just knows but does not understand the standard operating procedures of his job, then surely the employee will not know the full input, process up to the output of his work. Employees will not assume that their work is their responsibility, from the time the work is done until the work is completed. Such employees cannot possibly provide excellent service to patients. The results of the study stated that there was a relationship between task identity and service excellence. Chi square analysis showed that there was a relationship between task identity and the excellent service of Tiom Hospital employees in 2017 with p at 0.007. The existence of excellent service

relationships tends to be given by employees who have a high task identity but this is not meaningful. There is a relationship between task identity and excellent service employees, because there are still employees who do not have clear job descriptions or responsibilities and are poured into the job description. In addition there is no socialization of the Operational Standards. A clear procedure for each employee in accordance with his work, influencing employees in providing excellent service. This study also shows that there is a small difference in proportion between employees who have a low task identity and do not provide excellent service with employees who have a high duty identity and do not provide excellent service.

Relationship between Significance of Duty and Excellent Service of Employees

The results of this study indicate that service is not prime, it is actually more done by employees with high task significance than employees with low task significance of 20 employees (66.7%). This was allegedly because Tiom Hospital staff did not make high-duty significance as a reference to provide excellent service to patients, but only served as an excuse to provide modest service. The higher the meaning of one's work for the organization and other people around it, the employee will feel that the good and bad work done is not a problem the job is done. High task significance should increase employee responsibility to be able to increase its efforts in providing excellent service so that patients and colleagues feel more satisfied with the results of their work that improves.

The absence of a meaningful relationship was found between the significance of the task and excellent service, because every profession and service unit in the Tiom Regional General Hospital had a very important meaning for the success of excellent service at Tiom Regional General Hospital which led to patient satisfaction. If one of the professions

and service units does not provide excellent service, then the excellent service that has been carried out by the profession and other units is less impressive in the heart of the patient. High task significance shows that almost all employees of RSUD Tiom have considered that their work is important. However, this has not been supported by the excellent service culture that is owned by Tiom Regional Hospital and the employee's own personal.

Relationship between Autonomy and Excellent Service of Employees

The results of this study show the same thing, not excellent service is given more by employees with lower autonomy than employees with high autonomy as many as 22 employees (71%), this is because the Tiom Hospital staffs always have to complete the work in accordance with the direction of the supervisor and the applicable regulations. When providing services to patients, employees have almost no gaps to be able to do according to employee initiatives or decisions. Almost all activities that must be carried out by employees in giving employees have been regulated by applicable laws and regulations (for medical services) and / or supervisor regulations. The results of the study stated that there was a relationship between autonomy and excellent service of employees. The relationship between autonomy and excellent service of employees shows that the low level of employee autonomy in completing work does not rule out the possibility for some employees to have decisions and initiatives in providing excellent service. So that it can provide added value in serving patients to achieve excellent service.

Relationship between Feedback and Excellent Service of Employees

The results of this study do not show the same thing, not excellent service is mostly done by employees with low feedback compared to employees who have high feedback as many as 21 employees

(80.8%). This is because feedback obtained by employees is limited to performance appraisals obtained by employees in the form of the number of regional performance allowances with information on the level of employee performance. For Tiom Hospital employees who are contract workers, reports of daily activities are reported to the head of the unit at the beginning of each month to be assessed. The daily report is then accumulated into a piece of paper containing the type of work that the employee does and the quantity. After that the head of the unit and the chair of the service coordinator conferred to provide a value of behavior. BHU sheets that have been completed are given a value, then collected into the staffing section to be entered into the calculation or performance appraisal format. Good and bad performance is not directly conveyed to employees, so employees do not know the shortcomings in providing services and things that need to be improved so that they can provide excellent service to patients. Leaders only evaluate the achievement of employees in serving patients, but do not evaluate the services provided by employees to patients routinely and more specifically. As long as employees who have not provided excellent service do not know what they lack and feel they are good enough in providing services.

The results showed that there was a relationship between feedback and excellent service of employees. Chi square analysis shows that there is no feedback relationship with excellent service employees. The existence of a relationship between feedback with excellent service employees shows that the provision of feedback made by the hospital management is less effective, so that it cannot clearly describe what points are already good and which still need improvement. The lack of clarity resulted in employees not being able to know the assessment of the services they provided.

Relationship between Organizational Commitment and Employee Excellent Service

The results of this study do not show the same thing, not excellent service is mostly done by employees with high organizational commitment compared to employees with low commitment as many as 18 employees (94.7%). The condition of the crowded Tiom District Hospital every day requires employees to be able to survive providing services to patients. Coupled with various patient characteristics, ranging from impatient patients to queuing up to patients who will complain or protest if the service they receive is unsatisfactory. This clearly requires employees to have high organizational commitment and not just words and attitudes, but manifested through behavior that is by providing excellent service.

The results of the study show that there is a relationship between organizational commitment and excellent service of employees. Employees who do not realize organizational commitment will truly feel burdened to provide excellent service. This can then gradually diminish the commitment of formerly high employee organizations and not minimize the possibility of employees to stop or leave Tiom Hospital. Whereas for employees with low organizational commitment, things that are suspected to influence them not to provide excellent service, namely the values and objectives of employees are not in line with the values and goals of the organization. So that in providing excellent service, employees feel burdened because they do not understand well the importance of excellent service for Tiom Hospital and patients.

Relationship between Relationship between Employees and Excellent Service Employees

The results of non-prime service research are mostly done by employees who have a low relationship with co-workers compared to employees who have a high

relationship with co-workers as many as 18 employees (69.2%). This shows that a good relationship with co-workers is not the only thing that can affect an employee's positive mood and emotions. Another factor that can affect the primacy of services provided by employees can be due to the workload that is too large, saturated with monotonous work, or even family problems. Good relationships with colleagues in the environment can negatively affect the work done by employees. Employees who have a low level of awareness and concentration in work, will abuse the good relationship by chatting or even joking when providing services. This situation does not only prevent the employee from being able to provide excellent service, but can be an obstacle for employees who work in the same environment to be able to provide excellent service.

The results of the study stated that there was no relationship between the relationship of colleagues and the excellent service of employees. Chi square analysis showed that there was no relationship between the relationship of colleagues and the excellent service of Tiom Hospital employees because of the faction or group between service units believed to influence the results of the study. Employees tend to assess their kinship relationships based on their relationship with co-workers in one unit that relates to them every day, without considering relations with other employees outside their service units.

Relationship between Leadership and Excellent Service

The results of the study showed that low service excellence was mostly done by employees with low headroom leadership compared to 21 employees with high leadership. Leaders who have good relations with employees and do not show the level of position (superiors and subordinates) are often considered employees as an opportunity to not provide maximum service, because it is based on the thought that good leaders will understand any

shortcomings or errors of employees without giving a strong reprimand for deficiencies or the mistake. In addition, there is no reward system (award) from leaders to employees who excel and / or provide excellent service (excellent service), causing employees to not have the motivation to be able to provide the best service. The results of the study stated that there was a relationship between leadership and excellent service of employees. There is a relationship between leadership and excellent service employees allegedly due to a gap felt by some employees towards the leadership of the Hospital Director.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study concluded as follows:

- There is an age relationship with excellent service at Tiom District Hospital Lanny Jaya District (p-value = 0.006; RP = 2.402; CI95% = 1.201 - 4.804)
- There was no significant relationship between gender and excellent service at Tiom District Hospital Lanny Jaya District (p-value = 1,000; RP = 0.947; CI95% = 0.564 - 1.591).
- There is no significant relationship between education with excellent service at Tiom District Hospital Lanny Jaya District (p-value = 0.488; RP = 1.267; CI95% = (0.771 - 2.081)
- There is no significant relationship between the working period and excellent service at Tiom District Hospital Lanny Jaya District p-value = 0.283; RP = 1.510; CI95% = (0.785 - 2.903).
- There is a relationship of various skills with excellent service at Tiom District Hospital Lanny Jaya District (p-value = 0,000; RP = 19,286; CI95% = 2,851 - 130,455).
- There is an assignment identity relationship with excellent service at Tiom District Hospital Lanny Jaya District (p-value = 0.007; RP = 3.095; CI95% = 1.122 - 8.535).

- There is no correlation between task significance and excellent service at Tiom District Hospital Lanny Jaya District p-value = 0.226; RP = 1,500; CI95% = 0,844 - 2,666)
- There is an autonomous relationship with excellent service at Tiom District Hospital Lanny Jaya District (p-value = 0.036; RP = 2.011; CI95% = 1.017 - 3.976).
- There is a feedback relationship with excellent service at RSUD Tiom, Lanny Jaya District (p-value = 0.002; RP = 2.538; CI95% = 1.339 - 4.813).
- There is a relationship between organizational commitment and excellent service at Tiom District Hospital Lanny Jaya District (p-value = 0,000; RP = 2,747; CI95% = 1,645 - 4,588)
- There is no relationship between colleagues and excellent service at Tiom District Hospital Lanny Jaya District (p-value = 0.170; RP = 1.523; CI95% = (0.901 - 2.574)
- There was a leadership relationship between the Head of the Room and excellent service at Tiom District Hospital Lanny Jaya District (p-value = 0.013; RP = 2.143; CI95% = (1.136-441).

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